

Social Politics in the Selected Poems of E. E. Cummings and Ray Young Bear

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Abstract

This paper explores the symbols and images of using lowercase in the selected poems: Cummings' "who are you little i?" and Ray Young Bear's "Grandmother." These poets violate common orthographic rules by using only lowercase letters in these poems; however, they pursue symbolic meanings in doing so. Cummings' poems, which are presented in lowercase, signify a particular idiosyncrasy of orthography. This structural novelty [or innovation] makes a long-lasting impression on Cummings' readers and contributes to the enduring impact of his poetry. For Bear, this is symbolic in that the lowercase means Native Americans, the Mesquaki tribe, in North America construed in social politics. The Mesquaki and other Native American tribes faced discrimination and domination from Euro-American settlers and colonialists, as well as their descendants, for several generations. The purpose of this paper is to enhance the indirect meanings of images and influence of Native Americans, such as the Mesquaki people, who have been fighting for their identities in America for a long time. The related purpose is to enable readers to understand the experimental poetic tropes of Cummings and Bear, and "inform readers through experimental tropes" literally indicates that the author of this paper will use experimental tropes to inform the readers. This is qualitative research. The study focuses on: Why do the poets use lowercase in their poems? Why are poetic languages more complex than general languages? This study adopts symbol theory methods for discussion, and the research methodology of the poem is based on textual analysis.

Keywords: *equal rights, grammar, identity, lowercase, sociopolitical.*

Suggested citation: Gurung, R.K., & Sharma, B.D. (2024). Social Politics in the Selected Poems of E. E. Cummings and Ray Young Bear. *European Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 1(6), 133-143. DOI: 10.59324/ejahss.2024.1(6).14

Received: 14 September 2024

Reviewed: 28 October 2024

Published: 1 November 2024

Introduction

The study critiques the social politics of using experimental poetic tropes in Cummings' "who are you little i?" and Bear's "Grandmother" through the uses of symbols and images like lowercase. Both of the poets violated the grammar rules and used only the lowercase. There was politics in doing so. Cummings revealed a quirk of syntax. His intention is just to coin the newness. He protested the unconventional use of capitalization. Dylan Thomas also violated rules like "This Bread I Break," as an odd structure of the 'object first and subject-verb' pattern that is never excused by grammar. According to the traditional grammar rule, it should be "I break this bread." When he composed this poem, readers entertained it.

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Bear's "Grandmother" symbolizes Native Americans. Their social political or economic condition is the lowercase. The American Constitution does not seem to have addressed them in terms of their effects from social and political perspectives. The ruling class Americans discriminate against and dominate them by depriving them of backwards and uncivilized ones. This is how ruling-class Americans seem to have othered North Americans. Therefore, the poet has raised the voice of the Mesquaki tribe in North America. Thus, the lowercase is the symbolic presentation. On the other hand, Bear's (2015) poem is the voice of the misrepresentation of North Americans.

Poetry is a supreme form of expression with aesthetic and artistic elements. Poetic language has an appealing expression and memorable quality. In this regard, Kriszner & Mandel state:

To the ancient Greeks and Romans, poetry was the medium of spiritual and philosophic expression. Epics such as Illiad and Anneid are written in verse, as are dramas such as Oedipus the King. The Bible, Koran, and Hindu holy books are also written in poetry. Today, throughout the world, poetry continues to delight and inspire. For many people in many places, poetry is the language of emotions, the medium of expression they use from the heart. (2000, p.22)

Poetic art is universal and old and captures literary attention. Such beauty and the sonic effect of language attract and enlighten the readers. The poetic expression effectively transmits serious spiritual, religious and philosophical messages. This shows that all literary forms are not free from poetic expression. All the Bible, Koran, and Hindu holy books contain the poetic language. These holy books give several lessons and moral guides to the people. The people remember the inspirational verses of these books so that they implement them in their day-to-day lives maintaining discipline.

Materials and Methods

The study employs the document analysis methods to analyze the texts. The materials for this discussion are the poems composed by Ray Young Bear and E. E. Cummings. Their poems are written in lowercase and they are symbolic. According to Bear, Native Americans who live in North America are lowercase. As lowercase represents the lower values, so does the condition of the Mesquaki tribe. Cumming's indication is also almost the same but his is slightly different. In a sense, he also represents the lower value of a little boy in his poem "who are you little i?". Whereas, his "Buffalo Bill's" in which the words are scattered, is not only written in lowercase but also the segregated mentality of modern people.

*Buffalo Bill's defunct
who used to
ride a water smooth-silver
stallion. (line 1-5)*

This verse structure is uncommon although all the poetic language is not so. The structure of this poem looks like a pistol. Buffalo Bill is a hunter who used to hunt buffalo by riding a horse carrying a hunting weapon like a pistol.

Discussion and Results

In modern times, poetic literature is not merely an expression of ornate expressions and aesthetic perspectives of writing it is also a somewhat pragmatic way of expressing things that expose social and cultural realities in a peculiar way that sparks the readers' minds. The use of lowercase in the "who are little i?" and "GRANDMOTHER" has similar objectives. The way literature, like poetic writing, most of the time, makes us of covert ideas that cannot easily be penetrated through simple interpretation to get the meanings or the simple interpretation does not dig into the depth of the intended meaning.

The poets and writers make use of indirect use of expressions through metaphorical presentation. The use of images and symbols is common. For that purpose, they try to use stylistic variations and diverse ways of expression. Many of these techniques are used, and they are developed in the modern age, such as poetic techniques called defamiliarization, minimalism, typographical expressions, cubic expressions, syntactic diversions, and prose writing. These techniques sound playful because readers need to pore meanings not just from the surface level but from the depth. The real meaning of any text is not at the surface level. Poetic expression is for highly academic readers and beyond general readers.

The major concern of this paper was to enhance the sociopolitical condition of the Mesquaki tribe of North America as well as several other tribes who are in the condition of these native Americans. Therefore, Bear's poem is about the identity crisis. "GRANDMOTHER" raises the voice of North Americans whose identities have not been addressed by the American Constitution. For example, "The House passed the bill 86 to 37, over the objection of Democrats who opposed "receiving a black man on an equality with the white men of this country." On June 5, 1862, Lincoln signed the bill" (Masur, 2012, p. 31). It is Abraham Lincoln's Emancipation Proclamation in 1862 declared that there was equality between black men and white men but there was no equality till 1963. The discrimination was as usual. The way how the white people dominated the black people was as usual. It was after 101 years. In Washing D. C. "In 1963, the year that Martin Luther King, Jr., delivered one of the most famous speeches in American history, blacks in America lived under a racial caste system"(Hansen, 2003, P. 1). Similarly, the Mesquaki tribe in North America also lived under a racial caste system or they were in a pathetic condition. Because of the discrimination, their lifestyle was worsened as they were not given equal opportunities by the system. Therefore, their clothes were limited to purple scarves and plastic shopping bags, as the Mesquaki tribe woman was called a stereotypical Indian grandmother. These scarves and plastic bags are the cheapest items that the working- class people use them. They cannot purchase leather shopping bags and expensive scarves. This is why Ray Young Bear sheds light on this point North Americans, who are native people, are treated as the lowercase.

Poetic language is sonic: it can influence several people in a speech that is articulate and effective. Since it has a way of making sound use of language and structure and is poetic, it has an emphatic influence in that one likes to share and say the most sentimental and sensitive life issues. Good poetry is lapped with the greater domain of social acceptability because it makes the message widespread. For this reason, several great poets choose phenomenally intrusive verse expressions. According to Arnold (1985), "The best poetry is what we want; the best poetry will be found to have a power of forming, sustaining, delighting us, as nothing else can" (p. 68). What he means by this is the best poetry is what makes poetic form readable and perfectly poetic in terms of its form and content. What further he wants to indicate is that a good poetry full composite of formative ingredients like metaphor, symbols, and imageries that give a nice build in articulating perfect meaning that is both sonic and content-wise clear. Even if some people do not understand the deeper meaning at once, they enjoy poetry's formative basis. However, language's base and formative level are social and cultural issues.

Writing quaint poetry in the realm, of experimental poetic writing began with so much experimentation in English poetry. Many males and females were roused with several traces of experimentation: male and female diversity, cultural and social upheavals, economic disparity, political debates, and several other fronts. This experimentation began with the debate of whether poetic writing is just a linguistic entity or whether poetic writing has validity with sophistication. This debate, followed by poetic writing, has led to phenomenal growth in the expansion of poetic beauty, especially in the creation of vast possibilities of critical and literary possibilities. In this same vein, as with other creative genres, poetic writings took their vogue involving several creative writers whose critical and creative opinions marked the ground for further enhancement of this kind. Linda A Kinnahan (1996) has studied women's poetic writing trends in her essay and makes a point indicating that feminist writing and debates it postulates among poets and critics is much of interest not only to the writers and poets whose writings it underlines. Rather, it tried to provide space. Kinnahan (1996) specifically states:

A look at the political and artistic context in which these women write reveals important appropriations of and reactions to contemporary theory in their work with language and subjectivity, in their reactions to the masculine domain of British poetic tradition, and in their negotiations with both the socialist materialist bent of the British intellectual left and the capitalist conservatism of the Thatcherite and legacy. (p. 621)

The debate on the political, social, and economic dimensions grounded itself in the cry of the time. The women not only opened up a sense of grudge but also brought the whole of creative writing and critical thinking into engaging in the propagation of poetic quests and overall arguments of experimentation. These movements and many others were epochs allowing ground or many to work on further. Literary language is virtually metaphorical. It connects with several interpolations that words and images associate.

As far as experimentation continues, American poets have made a significant drive with several aspects of experimentation, making poetic writing diverse and rich with ample sophistication in terms of style, form, and linguistic criteria, as well as in the process of thought patterns. Some of these poetic writings were covered, as they had a deep foundation to percolate into the social, cultural, and political dynamics of societies. However, some of them were quietly able to draw the attention of the critics and overall impressions of their leaders. That is, the traditional dimension of poeticism, especially its formalistic and stylistic composition, should not be considered. Rather, the theme and critical texture it tries to embody took its domain. Bear (2015) and Cummings (2020) came to sway with their epoch-making experimentation. It is Bear who:

raised the sociopolitical issue, whereas Cummings used a new style in poetry writing. Cummings's use of lowercase means the creativity of the child is more effective than the grown-ups. This is an imagist trend of poetry as English poetry in the mid-twenties, ushered by Ezra Pound, William Carlos Williams, and E. E. Cummings marks diversity, experimentation, and innovations with idiosyncratic syntactic composition. (Gurung, 2024, p.112)

This is defamiliarization in technique which sparks the readers' mind. Politics and poetry are matters of expression because both are ways of expression for the general people. We know that politicians are not direct: they also take some forms of expression that can give some ironic and paradoxical traits of languages whose meanings cannot be outright. This means that poets can say a lot in their metaphoric and symbolic expressions. We can take several such examples from political rhetoric, whether it is the speech given by a great statesman in England, such as Winston Churchill, who gave a speech in the House in the wake of the Second World War. We can also take examples of Martin Luther King's speech in his Gettysburg Address entitled "I Have a Dream".

Poetic language is often subtle; it does not reflect the thought as clearly as the river flows or the wind blows. It has its way of exposing formative ingredients. The poetic language is full of analogies and contradictions. On the one hand, it tries to project what it best can. On the other level of the plane, it tries to make things contradictory embroiling several social, cultural, and political components. Many later critics of the twentieth century like IA Richard, and Clinth Brooks, have held a notion that poetic language is full of paradoxes. This paradox embraces the formative layers of poetry. As Clinth Brooks (1985) make a point, "The poet must work by analogies, but the metaphors do not lie in the same plane or fit nearly edge to edge. There is a continual tilting of the planes; necessary overlapping, discrepancies, and contradictions. Even the Simple poet is forced into paradoxes far more often than we think if we are sufficiently alive to what he is doing." (p.322).

Furthermore, poetry and politics are based on public discourse and can influence public debate and ideas. Parini (2008) suggested that a poet's works are politically powerful because language poetry provides a deep understanding in a way that other writing does not.

Bam Dev Sharma (2023) claims, "any text has three basic elements: the linguistic component, the social component, and the factors that help define these components. These factors differ in situations because sometimes they are guided by ideologies and social and cultural contexts" (p. 34). The poetic text can invite an interpreter's approach, ranging from interdisciplinary, intertextual, and semiotic texts to general ones. One dominant aspect of English poetry is its interrelationship with politics and political ideology.

This has been traced even from a long time back as long as the Renaissance and restoration poetic writings took their veins.

Although politics did not stand only as the dominant theme, political rhetoric had its prevalence since the time of Plato, which became a cult of poetic writing even in modern times. Jacobson (2002) opines philosophically, "Poetry is organized violence committed on ordinary speech. That is, poetry both disturbs and reforms the pattern of routine language (cited in (Sharma, 2022, p. 48). Cummings and Bear use the lowercase in their poetries as their violence is organized violence that is excusable. To give a new taste to the readers, they use this strategy that it does not any negative connotation. Their politics is for the betterment. Cleanth Brooks (1947) states, "Few of us are prepared to accept the statement that the language of poetry is the language of paradox. Paradox is the language of sophistry, hard, bright, witty; it is hardly the language of the soul" (Brooks, 1947, p. 3). Most of the poetic language is paradoxical. They are presented through words but the above-mentioned two poets use lowercase for similar purposes.

English and American poetry are rife with political issues that are ingrained into society. When we read British poetry, we find political elements. When Horatian Ode was written in 1650, it was considered one of the fertile grounds for depicting prevailing political conflicts in societies. According to common considerations, many of these poems, including that of Andrew Marvel, indicated political unrest in society regarding the conflict between the royalists and those with the supporters of Oliver Cromwell, who was rising as a reformer, claiming that the royalist model of literature was leading society into artistic and cultural downfalls. Andrew Marvel, in many of his poems, is considered a royalist in literary expositions, although he did not show any interest in politics. When Charles I was executed in 1650, parliamentarians led by Oliver Cromwell made several reformatations. However, this led to another dark realm of conflict that was indicated by the development of another trend called the Glorious Revolution of 1688, which punished the Puritan norms and values of society.

With this historical ground, poetry and politics are intricately related in many writings of eminent poets as long as we come to the modern era of W.H. Auden, especially referring to his poem entitled "September 1, 1939". This poem highlights the great dynamic of the time, especially the melancholic nature of societies rife with immoral values, conflicting global politics, and societies driven by short-sighted views of political demagogues. Auden satirizes the complete pictures of times that bore hostile relationships and the downfall of values that tightened humanity once loosening grounds. Stephen Burt (2003), a famous critic, points out that poetry and society are not separate, especially concerning Auden's poem. The title of the poem itself marks the deadly scenario of the Second World War. To some extent, this poem refers to the emaciation of values but rising hostilities that broke not only nations but also human minds and emotions (533-559).

Moreover, perhaps in the name of maintaining the standard, poets use complex languages. Sometimes, the readers do not understand the denotative and connotative meanings. In this context, critical discourse analysis may help go into the depth of meaning. "However, critical discourse analysis is not an absolute approach; it can be just a relative approach of gathering meaning through different micro and macro elements inherent in the texts" (Sharma, 2023, p. 34). This approach helps gather meanings through different micro and macro elements from the texts. As is put:

Part of the problem is that poetry has many guises: a poem may be short or long, accessible or obscure; it may express a mood or tell a story; it may conform to familiar poetic form ---a sonnet, a couplet, a haiku---or follow no conventional pattern; it may or may not have a regular, identifiable meter or rhyme scheme; it may depend heavily on elaborate imagery, figures of speech, irony, complex allusions or symbols, or repeated sounds---or it may include none of these features conventionally associated with poetry. (Kriszner & Mandell, 2005, p.522)

Another dominant poet of significant stature is Wallace Stevens, whose soft-spoken voice and paradoxical and ironic compositions hint at the political message. Many of his poems try to expose social order and times and indicate that the order of life and values are not in the proper place to ensure that mankind's comfortable stride is desired. His poetic collection, entitled *The Ideas of Order*, is a nice collection of thirty-six poems with political messages. The poems, though they are not congruent, mark

themes of politics and times, politics and social order, politics and religion, politics and morality. All these poems are remarkably set in social and political mosaics to open up human conscience at large and social order in particular. In the words of Joseph N. Riddel (1965):

The Ideas of Order in its final form, however, represent a concern for order that is more politically immediate than the exercises of Harmonium. Although Stevens cannot be said to have given a way to leave, he has for the time adapted himself to the realities of the period, and attempted to bring the extremely personal search of Harmonium into some immediate relation with social crisis. (p. 336)

Writing in idea of order might be Utopian concept in a sense but writing in disorder like using only lowercase reflects the political chaos and a kind of anarchic scenario of the world. All the political leaders see the general public the lowercases that is inferred from their behaviours. Harmonious relation is just hollowness. There lies the harmonious relations that is what social crisis is.

Analysis of the Poem from a Social-Political Perspective

We know that the root of any literature is part of sharing between speakers and readers, who can utilize language not only for its beauty and aesthetic delight. The esthetic delight of poetic language is short-lived because one cannot remain transfixed for a longer time. There comes the message part: the inner dynamics of poetry. This inner dynamic is controlled by several elements, prominently social, political, and cultural issues. An indisputable argument is that a political message in any genre is considered a powerful tool for hearing a speech by Martin King Luther's "I Have Dream" or any epic poem by great poets such as Milton, Alfred Lord Tennyson, or T.S. Eliot. It seems that the great works of poetry make things so grand that these images remain in the minds of the people. At the same time, such poetic writings also influence us. Modern poetic writing, in this sense, is not just verbose: it is economical and terse because modern readers are not merely swayed by ornate words. Therefore, modern poetry is predominantly construed as a social and political phenomenon. J. Paul & Hunter (1998), "In poems, ideas, and feelings are packed tightly into just a few lines. The experiences of life are very concentrated here, and meanings emerge quickly, word by word. Poems often show us the very process of putting feelings into language that can be shared with others . . . to say feelings in a communicable way"(p.597).

Against this backdrop, the following poem entitled "Buffalo Bill's" can be analysed as the most representative poem, reflecting the entire trend of the imagist movement.

*Buffalo Bill's defunct
who used to
ride a water smooth-silver
tallion
and break
one two three four five pigeons just like that
Jesus
he was a handsome man
and what I want to know is
how do you like your blue-eyed boy
Mister Death*

This jig jag structure of the poem is symbolic of jig jag modes of the modern world where everyman has to be careful or s/he may lose his/her path. Once you lose your path you will not reach to your destination. Similarly, this figure reflects "the denoising of life" (Gurung, 2024, p. 114). Moreover, Gurung clarifies, "Rife with descriptive imagery, as if the painter illustrates picturesque colourful shades,

the poem breaks away ensuing into unique verbal expressions. The imageries and descriptions swirl as if the gnats in the sky like the words rider, stallion, pigeons, Jesus, and speaker, who appear as the observer of all the phenomena” (p.114) reflect the mundane lives and unavoidable deaths of living beings. This is how this poem represents the equality among diverse realities and universality.

The equation of power and powerlessness often collide, always proving the powerful as the warrior winning the war of life. To some extent, this can be taken as something of class and classless people whose distinct roles are reflected in social and cultural life. The man has a ferocious hunting thirst and he kills the helpless birds like pigeons as well as swans. This is indicative that here several helpless creatures who are often defenceless against the brutal force that can prove their pride and dignity in the social and cultural milieu. Gurung again presents that “This probably implies the atrocity of war and its menace” (p. 114) worldwide. The figure indicates several meanings. The dispersed and integrated word or words in the poem like “onetwothreefourfivepigeonsjustlikethat” indicate the modern make of society. This shows that some people are living so closely, whereas some are separated in such a way that they do not want to see each other. This integrated word shows unmanaged city life on one hand, on the other hand, it represents the unhealthy closeness because of benefit. The uniqueness is illustrated by colours such as "water smooth" silver stallion" "blue ". . . manifest pictorial sense and connect the theme of universality, purity, virginity, and a sense of eternity. The casual remark "Mister Death" is ironic and sardonic, the vibrancy of life (p.114).

However, all the writers do not violate the grammar rules. There is politics of using the lower cases violating the conventional rules. This paper examines two poems: Cummings’ “who are you little i?” and Bear’s “Grandmother.” This is a newness to the readers and at the same time satirize the realities in different ways. In addition to these two poets, Dylan Thomas also violated the grammar in his poem, “This Bread I Break.” This sentence is grammatically wrong, but it gives a new taste to the readers. It was a good technique for Thomas. Unlikely, Cummings tricks in punctuation. In “who are you little i?”, the speaker is talking to a little child of five or six who is looking out through the window at dusk, and it is a beautiful scene of nature that has attracted him. It is the child’s attraction toward the beauty of nature, although s/he does not know that beauty has the power of attraction. Landles opines, “[t]he childish awakening from a state of innocence to knowledge is not detected by all critics” (p.33). Every child awakens from a state of innocence to knowledge that this is the process of development of the human mind. The child symbolizes innocence and adult knowledge. So might be the old age. Cummings presents a poem such as this:

who are you, little i
(five or six years old)
peering from some high
window; at the gold
of November sunset (Lines 1—5)

In these lines of the poem, all the words are lowercase, which indicates the little innocent child who is looking out a high window at sunset. In the poem, the character “the little i” suggests the littleness caused by war, although there is no direct context of war. The little child who is five or six years old is peering through a high window symbolizing his hope of maybe peace. The coldness of November represents not only the physical coldness or severe cold of the winter season but also the political coldness between different countries. The child grows fast. Similarly, people’s wish to achieve a better situation also increases quickly, as spring occurs after winter. The sunset, or the evening, symbolizes the child’s hope of ending the war. This meaning can be drawn from these lines and the feeling that if day/has to become night/this is a beautiful way (p. 6-8).

This is a natural process in which a day becomes a night, and this indicates the child’s wish to end the war as soon as possible. The evening shows that the war is almost over, and after every bad time, the good time comes. The world swings between good and bad even though people want only the good.

Why does the poet, Cummings, show the child's hope of the process of a day beautifully becoming night? This line, "a beautiful way," indicates that the child is never hopeless. Their dream is never small. The little child seems to hope that the war inculcates not only the destruction but also the construction after the downfall of cruel rulers such as Hitler. This also shows that war is a necessary evil even if it is a man-eating monster.

This poem also reflects William Wordsworth's poem, "My Heart Leaps Up When I Behold" (52). It is a child whose heart leaps up when he beholds the rainbow in the sky, but he does not know why it happens. The beauty of nature has attracted him. He also does not know that natural beauty has the power of attraction. Cummings claims "that children are usually more spontaneous and creative than grown-ups" (37). The child in his poem observed the sunset, which impacted his/her mind. This helps him/her create something unpredictably new ideas that benefit the masses, as "child is the father of a man" said Wordsworth. This scene may not make an age-old man eighty at the same rate. The eighty-year-old man may not create anything from such natural beauty because they have limited desires, whereas children are more curious and excited as well as more creative.

The only difference between these two poems is that the child in Cummings' poem is silent and, in Wordsworth's poem, is jumping with joy looking at the rainbow in the sky. The child in Cummings's poem is physically silent but not psychologically silent. He is peering through a high window, which means that he is trying to create a new idea. This high window indicates his superb idea that will benefit the masses. The child leaps up with joy when he sees the rainbow in the sky. Wordsworth (1802) recites:

My heart leaps up when I behold: A rainbow in the sky; So was it when my life began; So is it now when I am a man; So will it be when I shall grow old, (lines 1—4)

This is how Wordsworth's child jumps with happiness, whereas Cummings' child does not jump, but his inner desires are not as silent as his physical actions are. His silence will surely be changed into restlessness. Here, the context is different, but the child's nature is almost the same. In Cummings's poem, the child's silence suggests a separate mentality because of war destruction. Although his silence does not last long, he is disturbed. The study does not discuss the overwhelming condition of a child, but the child in Cummings's poem also wanted to expand like a child in the poem "My Heart Leaps Up When I Behold" after the situation of war improved. He seems to be waiting for that moment. His silence is momentary.

Both poets have violated the grammar rules and used only the lowercase in these poems, as there is politics in doing so. Cummings' poems, which have been composed in lowercase, show how a particular idiosyncrasy of syntax clicks the public mind. It is a structural newness to the readers so that his poetry can be sustained in the field of English literature, although not all poets apply this method. This technique presents a kind of distinctness. Cummings presents a new style of writing poetry with unconventional capitalization. For Bear (2015), this is symbolic in that the lowercase represents Native Americans, the Mesquaki tribe, in North America. They have been discriminated against and deprived by the ruling class of Americans. He states that the metaphorical presentation of lowercase represents North Americans. Bear's (2015) poem is the voice of North Americans for equal rights and identity crisis. The findings of the study show that this practice in America is still ongoing, although constitutionally, it has been settled. This shows that almost all North Americans are working-class people. The purpose of this paper is to enhance the sociopolitical condition of such segregated people who are fighting for their identities and to inform readers about a new style of using lowercase in poetry. This is qualitative research. This study adopts document analysis methods for discussion.

This paper analyses the sociopolitical context in Cummings' poetry. Many imagist poets for example, William Carlos Williams and Ezra Pound are not only the precursors of the imagist movements, as experimental aesthetics of the time but also tried to break away from the esthetic concept prevailing in their times. Their epoch-making poetic writings, unique and stylistically rich, also projected social and cultural issues of the time. The critics call them culture critics. There are several justifications made by critics who hold the notion that they are trying to react against the capitalistic and affluent class, thereby

advocating justice, equal rights, and equitable opportunities for all in society. The complexities of the shocking results of the First World War and the degeneration of values substantiate this fact. Their outstanding remarks in contemporary societies thus seem to be reflected in poetic writings. Loss of value, excessive materialistic quests, and power and influence to determine humanistic values are some of the undercurrent aspects that draw the attention of people. The widening gap between affluent and less affluent classes has led to social and cultural unrest. In addition, a large portion of societies are experiencing hardships and difficulties in terms of survival and necessities.

Another relevant interpretation may be that all the people became small letters after the great wars, as several powerful countries became powerless or several towers were broken down. The use of lowercase symbolizes this reality, too. Several towering countries came down, socially, financially, morally, politically, and culturally, and several such leaders. Therefore, lowercase is the permanent place where the entire world can adjust to it. These poets then satirize and compose the poems in lowercase as everyone's last stage. The USSR-like country almost collapsed, as did Japan. To symbolize these realities, the poets seem to have used the lowercase in their poetries. Poetic language is different from the language of a story or novel. Poetry is beyond the prediction of the general human mind. Harry Blamires states that [p]oetry's true function is 'the winning of the mind from wickedness to virtue' (56). The poetic language can even convince wicked-minded persons, and they can turn into virtue. Therefore, poetry has that power.

Against this backdrop, it can be easily deduced that these poets, most prominently, e.g., Cummings and Ray Young Bear (2015), seem to be concerned with sociopolitical issues. Several of their writings reflect that. For this purpose, the following section takes into account E.E. Cummings's poetry and how it is embedded with a sociopolitical dimension. Tartakovsky states, "Cummings derived his style from the earlier phases of Modernism of the 1910s, with a particular emphasis on the Imagist movement" (p. 217). His poetry manifests stylistic distortions with a particular emphasis on the Imagist movement. He uses idiosyncratic structures that look quite quaint as if he is playful and not serious.

However, this is not the case because he is greatly dismayed by the conflicting wars and their wounds in human lives. In addition, he is also not happy with the progress society makes in the names of rights and democratic institutions, for all these rights and institutions are just on paper and they have not made any drastic transformation in societies. Poetically, his lines reflect the social and cultural chaos of society. Since his poetic lines are short and long, human beings, in society, are divided in the same spirit of value distortion and lack equality, trust, and confidence. There is a large gap in human beings in terms of class, wealth, social upbringing, and values. Cummings is critical of the progress society has made. After the havoc of the First World War, society did not have its usual pace, and it was the most volatile time in human history. Several rising conflicts were created by class, social, and political consciousness. The conflict between right and left, rich and poor, affluent and less affluent, capitalistic and non-capitalistic modes shadowed humanitarian and universal values.

There is another facet of Cummings' poetry to justify society's social and political issues. In his poetry, we find that he is using all the small letters without capitalizing the letters that were required according to grammar. This is a rhetorical device because he dreams of a society that should not be class and human and that everybody should treat others in the same position. Mondello (2011) specifically states this:

deliberate choice of small-scale participation in the political spirit of the counterculture sparked the modernist desire to overturn previously held ideas and beliefs. This revolutionary consciousness created a climate ripe for change in values such as valorization of the small. (p. 36)

We also see another dimension of E.E. Cummings's poetry which is described as masculine pride in his poetry because all his groups were masculine friends who took part in the movement. This, too, can be analysed as his rhetorical strategy. He never believed in a society that can be divided into gender and class consciousness. However, many of the poems of this trend seem to be connected with social and cultural issues of the time. For this campaign, they engaged in the movement of the fraternity as revolutionaries

who could not feel easy with the times. They wanted to raise their voices because all wars and conflicts are the result of wrong notions of human sentimentality and idolizing power:

Cummings' pacifism in a century full of devastating wars resulted in poems that eagerly attempt to confront and redefine masculinity. His poems battled the conventions which classified pacifism as not masculine. While his later poetry often presents a construct of the man of the sixties. Many of his earlier poems present the desolation and isolation of modern man while criticizing conventional male roles as outdated and ineffective. (Paganni & Kier, 1985, p. 155)

Cummings makes it clear that war has incredible impacts in poems that eagerly attempt to confront and redefine masculinity. Because of the great wars, masculine Japan has come down for some days. His poems have battled against the conventions that have classified nonviolence. The poet criticises the conventional male roles that are obsolete. His earlier poems present sadness and alienated obligation, possibly because of the overuse of machines. His poems also seem to symbolize an egalitarian society. The conventional male role involves discrimination against other nonmales. These messages can also be disseminated to the masses from his poems.

Conclusion

Social politics is a complex phenomenon that dominantly prevails in literary writing. However, analysing and interpreting it is more often conditioned by the pragmatic realities of society. This research explores social politics through experimental writings that can both entertain and paradoxically hint at societies. The use of lowercase highly indicates that images and symbols have more to say. One can draw thousands of meanings from the images or symbols. It depends on the intellect of a scholar. The selected poems “who are you little i?” by E. E. Cummings and “Grandmother” by Ray Young Bear are full of social politics. The poetic technique employed by the experimental poetic technique makes unique expressions while simultaneously combating social realities. For Bear, the lowercase symbolizes the Native Americans, the Mesquaki tribe, in North America. As the lowercase seems to be negligible, the Mesqueki tribe seems negligible there. Their economic and social status is pathetic. The majority of them are still working class rather than the ruling class or high class. Therefore, Bear's (2015) issue is the identity crisis stating that the lowercase represents North Americans.

North Americans' lives are languishing because they are not taken care of by the government as required. Their grip at the government level or in the administration is negligible despite their number and capabilities. The American constitution seems to recognize these issues but practically, the North Americans cannot have realized this yet. Their social status is lowercase. Therefore, the title is in capital or uppercase “GRANDMOTHER.” This is symbolic that the Mesqueki tribe wants a change, the uppercase. It is natural, too. Everyone does not like to stay in the same position all the time. The position of North Americans was and is still neglected.

E. E. Cummings' poem Buffalo Bill's symbolizes the neglected life of an entire human being. The purpose of this paper was to enhance the sociopolitical condition of North Americans who are fighting for their rights and identities and to inform readers about a new style of using the lowercase in poetry by Cummings. Originally, this was qualitative research. This study adopted document analysis methods for discussion and explored the usage of lowercase letters in the given poems in detail.

Contributions

Dr. Raj Kumar Gurung: Data analysis and interpretation of images and symbols

Mr. Bam Dev Sharma: Data collection and language editing

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